

A TECHNIQUE FOR THE MEASUREMENT OF PROCESS-INDUCED INTERNAL STRESSES IN POLYMERS AND POLYMER COMPOSITES

Paul Sunderland, Won J. Yu and Jan-Anders E. Månson
Laboratoire de Technologie des Composites et Polymères
Ecole Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne
CH-1015 LAUSANNE, Switzerland

ABSTRACT

The post-moulding properties and durability of a manufactured part are strongly influenced by the presence of process-induced internal stresses. Many previous studies have dealt with the prediction of internal stresses in a variety of materials, yet their measurement can be problematic, especially in materials with pronounced viscoelastic characteristics, such as polymer systems. A new technique, the 'Successive Grooving Technique', is proposed for the measurement of through-thickness internal stress profiles in polymers and polymer composites. It overcomes the drawbacks of previous methods as it requires no special specimen preparation, avoids excessive machining and can be applied to laminated materials.

INTRODUCTION

Internal stresses within polymeric materials have been much studied in the past, since they exert a predominant influence on the post-moulding behaviour of a manufactured part, both in terms of mechanical performance and durability. Through post-moulding relaxation of these stresses dimensional instability occurs and residual stresses remain. With the increased use of automated production processes, involving rapid moulding cycles and optimised process control, the need to determine and control internal stresses has become more apparent. This is especially true for high performance thermoplastic-matrix fibre composites. High levels of internal stress are to be expected in these materials given the high processing temperatures, unbalanced cooling profiles and high pressure gradients to which they are subjected during forming.

Many studies have concentrated on the analysis, numerical or otherwise, of internal stresses [1-4, for example]. The problem is complex; process and structure effects interact strongly and complicate the analysis. Few studies have concentrated on the measurement of internal stresses in manufactured composite parts. Many of the methods presently available are derived from techniques originally developed for metals. Three of the destructive methods so far proposed are the removal of a layer from a thick plate for skin/core stress measurement [5], the technique of hole drilling in relatively thin plate for planar internal stresses [6] and the PSL technique [7]. In these methods, measurement of internal stresses involves removal of some of the stressed material from the part. This releases the internal stresses sustained by the removed material, and the resulting modification of the stress field leads to changes in the geometry of the part as another self-equilibrating state of stress is attained. The internal stresses previously present within the removed material can thus be evaluated from the measurement of the strain field within the part or from the part deformation.

Three points of particular importance should be considered with these methods; the precision of the material removal process, the link between the internal stress component in the removed

material and the deformation of the remaining body, and the limitation of use to standard geometries well-described by simple analysis.

Several analytical techniques allow non-destructive observation of stress levels, among which Raman spectroscopy, acoustoelasticity and X-ray diffraction. However the application of these sophisticated techniques has so far remained limited to observation of surface and near-surface internal stress profiles, in a more qualitative than quantitative way.

For measuring stresses in a practical situation, only the PSL technique [7] could feasibly be employed for laminated composites of simple geometry, but it requires special preparation of the part. It is also time-consuming. A technique is needed for relatively straightforward and rapid analysis of production parts. With this in mind the Successive Grooving Technique (SGT) is proposed and its feasibility for the study of internal stresses investigated.

THE SUCCESSIVE GROOVING TECHNIQUE

THE NATURE OF INTERNAL STRESS

Internal stresses are by their very nature different from externally-induced stresses. While the latter are produced by and are in equilibrium with external load, either thermal or mechanical, internal stresses in a part are self-equilibrating, in that they counterbalance and constrain each other within the part. Thus, internal stresses are latent and are unlikely to manifest themselves until this self-equilibrating state is disturbed by external factors.

An imaginary distribution of internal stresses in a laminated composite sample, taken from a large component, is shown in Fig. 1. For the laminate to be free from distortion without any

Figure 1. Internal stresses in a laminated composite

external constraint, the internal stresses in the body should be in equilibrium, that is they should meet the general equilibrium conditions, which at a cross section of $x=x_0$ reduce to:

$$\sum F_x = \int_{z=-0.5h}^{z=0.5h} \sigma_{xx}(z) dA = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\sum M_y = \int_{z=-0.5h}^{z=0.5h} z^* \cdot \sigma_{xx}(z) dA = 0 \quad (2)$$

where h is the laminate thickness and z^* is the distance from an arbitrary reference plane (the neutral plane is usually selected).

The same equations may also be established with respect to the y -direction. When the built-in internal stresses of a part do not satisfy these conditions, which may, for example, occur when a component has just been removed from the mould, the part will warp or bend until the equilibrium conditions are satisfied. Non-uniform viscoelastic relaxation from an initial equilibrium internal stress state is also an important source of non-equilibrium conditions, in which case a gradual distortion of the component during its service life may be attributable to the process of internal stress re-equilibration. Thermal treatment of the part may also encourage such a redistribution, by promoting more rapid relaxation of stresses.

It should also be noted that the dominant normal internal stress component in a ply is constrained within the body by the shear stress component at the edge region. At the very edge of the laminate, that is the cut surface when the piece is removed from the larger laminate, a new, complicated, stress state evolves to attain equilibrium conditions under this boundary condition. However, since this edge effect zone is relatively small in accordance with Saint-Venant's principle, then attention can be focused on the body where the equilibrium state can be assumed to be maintained only by the normal stress component and the shear contribution to be negligible.

Stress release similar to this edge effect can also take place in the vicinity of local discontinuities in the body. Warpage associated with defects or microcracks due to localised fracture, which affect the local release of internal stress, have been described by previous studies as accounting for the stiffness change in crossply laminated beams [3]. This phenomenon of stress release may be exploited to measure internal stresses.

STRESS RELEASE INDUCED BY CUTTING A GROOVE

The proposed technique involves cutting a progressively deepening thin slit through the thickness of a part and measuring the part deformation after each new cut with a strain gauge placed on the face of the part opposite to the groove (Fig. 2). Cutting the groove modifies the overall stress field within the part and its geometry changes until another self-equilibrating

Figure 2. Experimental apparatus

state of stress is attained. From the strains measured by the strain gauge the internal stresses across the section can be calculated. The key advantage to the technique is that the self-equilibrating state of internal stresses is disturbed without significant material removal; essentially, the stress state changes while the overall part dimensions remain constant.

When a groove is cut parallel to the y -axis in the outer surface of the cross-section, the equilibrium stress state of the part is disturbed, and consequently some release of internal stresses results. The geometry of the groove (width b , depth d and tip shape) will influence the stress release. In general, the stress release will consist of two parts; firstly, of stresses in the groove material itself, which are fully removed from the body on removal of the material; and

secondly, of stresses near the groove, within a zone affected by the groove as shown in Fig. 3, where both local stress redistribution and global stress redistribution (within the part to satisfy the equilibrium conditions) occur.

Figure 3. The region around a groove

If the width of the groove is assumed to be sufficiently narrow, then the effect of material removal can be ignored, and a model for the evaluation of the internal stress field may be defined based only on the stress release in the zone affected by the groove.

THE TWO-DIMENSIONAL COMPLIANCE MODEL

Stress release around the groove promotes new stress and strain fields within the part. When the first groove is cut, to a depth of h_1 , the new stress field in the body is given by:

$$\sigma_1 = \sigma_0 - \sigma_{rel,1} \quad (3)$$

where σ_1 is the new stress field, σ_0 the initial stress field and $\sigma_{rel,1}$ the stress field released on cutting the first groove. The released stress field $\sigma_{rel,1}$ is a complex function of several factors:

$$\sigma_{rel,1} = f(\text{material, geometry, } b, d, \sigma_0, \dots) \quad (4)$$

where b and d are the groove width and depth respectively, and the strain field ϵ_1 caused by $\sigma_{rel,1}$ is:

$$\epsilon_1 = C \sigma_{rel,1} \quad (5)$$

where C represents the compliance. The internal stress field may be derived if its relation to the experimentally-measured strain field is known explicitly; this is done by solving the above equations. Certain simplifying assumptions can be used; firstly, constant stress across a cut thickness, which is permissible when the thickness of the part is considerably larger than that of each cut, and secondly linear elastic behaviour of the material and geometry. Then, the strain field and the released stress field can be simulated by applying external pressure of magnitude equal to that of the internal stress within that layer before the cut, to the groove wall. Thus, for σ_{xx} stresses:

$$\epsilon_1 = C_1 \sigma_{xx,1} \quad (6)$$

where C_1 is the compliance equal to the strain field produced by unit pressure applied at the cut wall.

This relationship is a generalised expression, which can be applied to more specific realistic cases. That is, a similar expression to Eqn (5) can be established for the value of the characteristic strain (average strain on the bottom surface in the zone affected by the groove):

$$\varepsilon_1^* = C_{11} \sigma_{xx,1} \quad (7)$$

where ε_1^* represents the characteristic strain and C_{11} the compliance coefficient (equal to the characteristic strain when unit pressure is applied at the groove wall).

This characteristic strain is measurable during cutting of successively deeper grooves through the part, using strain gauges, and the relationship between the characteristic strain and the initial internal stress in the first layer is thus defined.

Moreover, as the groove is cut deeper one thickness h_j at a time, the characteristic strain at the bottom surface of the part can be expressed as a series of compliance coefficients C_{ij} and the internal stress in each layer. When a groove is cut up to the i -th layer,

$$\varepsilon_i^* = \sum_{j=1}^i C_{ij} \sigma_{xx,j} \quad , j \leq i \quad (8)$$

where ε_i^* represents the characteristic strain when the groove is cut up to the i -th layer, $\sigma_{xx,j}$ the initial internal stress in the j -th layer and C_{ij} the compliance coefficient, equal to the characteristic strain when unit pressure is applied at the groove wall of the j -th layer while the groove is cut up to the i -th layer.

Knowing the set of compliance coefficients, internal stresses in each layer can be calculated from Eqn (9) using the measured strains on the bottom surface during the successive grooving. That is, the stress at the i -th layer can be derived as:

$$\sigma_{xx,i} = \frac{1}{C_{ii}} (\varepsilon_i^* - \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} C_{ij} \sigma_{xx,j}) \quad , j \leq i \quad (i=1,2,\dots,n) \quad (9)$$

Thus, the internal stress within each layer of the cross-section can be explicitly expressed as linear simultaneous equations. As is clear from Eqn (9), if the internal stress at the i -th layer is to be determined, then the groove should be cut *up to and including* that layer, and the characteristic strain and compliance coefficients should also be measured and calculated respectively up to that layer. It is worthwhile noting that the values of the compliance coefficients are dependent upon the length over which the characteristic strain is measured, and this should be chosen appropriately, taking into account factors such as part thickness, layer thickness, the stiffness of each layer and the dimensions of the available strain gauges.

NUMERICAL VERIFICATION

A numerical calibration of this analytical technique was carried out to determine the applicability of the two-dimensional compliance model. For a representative thermoplastic matrix composite, material and internal stress data on compression-moulded APC2/AS4 from Manson and Seferis [7] was used. The high cooling rates imposed during processing of these 40-ply laminates represent typical production moulding conditions. For these laminates, the parabolic skin/core internal stress field had been determined using three different techniques, of which mainly the Process Simulated Laminate (PSL) method.

In the finite element model used to represent the part, symmetry of the laminate and groove was assumed, so only a half length of the laminate was modelled as a set of 4-node plane strain elements. ABAQUS V5.3[®] was used for the analysis.

Initially, the set of compliance coefficients C_{ij} was determined by modelling a laminate containing no internal stress. This is a necessary step for each new material/geometry combination.

Then, to simulate the cutting of successively deeper grooves across the laminate, the horizontal constraints at the plane of symmetry were removed layer-by-layer. As the stress field is known in this case, a set of through-thickness characteristic strains could be generated, which could subsequently be combined with the compliance coefficients C_{ij} to re-calculate the internal stress profile. The correlation between the calculated values and those obtained by the measurement techniques in [7] was very good, and validated the 2-D compliance model approach.

MEASUREMENTS - RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Compression-moulded $[0_5, 90_{15}]$ laminates of PEI/GF of nominal thickness 3.2mm were cut into 65mmx10mm strips and a strain gauge placed on each specimen. Accuracy in the positioning of the gauge is essential, since the numerical model for stress calculation assumes alignment in both axes of the plane. A half-bridge Wheatstone bridge containing a compensator gauge was used, to avoid measurement of strain effects linked to temperature variation.

Each through-thickness stress profile requires the cutting of two specimens, one from each face up to the centre section. The cut depth was 0.16mm and its width 0.5mm, the nominal thickness of one ply, although this can be varied should the geometry of the part require. For each specimen the process of strain measurement, including initial set-up and calibration of the specimen, and stress calculation took roughly one hour.

Fig. 4 shows the values of the measured strains as a function of the depth of the cut.

Figure 4. Strain measurements on cutting one half of a $[0_5, 90_{15}]$ PEI/GF laminate

From these observed strains the stress profile across the section could be calculated, using the numerically-derived 2-D compliance coefficients for each cut layer and by taking a least squares approach for the measured strain values. Fig. 5 shows this profile, in comparison to a predicted profile obtained by an alternative numerical approach [8].

This alternative approach entailed calculation of the thermally-induced stresses in an anisotropic part, starting from the temperature distribution within the part as obtained from a two-dimensional representation of the heat equation, and by taking into account the

viscoelastic nature of the material with a Prony series expression for the relaxation modulus. ABAQUS V5.3[®] was used for the analysis.

Figure 5. Measured stress profile across the thickness of a [0₅, 90₁₅] PEI/GF laminate, compared to a predicted stress profile

It is apparent from the stress profile obtained by the Successive Grooving Technique that the use of strain gauges provides sufficiently high sensitivity to quantify thermal- and anisotropy-induced stress effects. The stress discontinuity at the interface is clearly brought to light. The slight shoulder visible at the specimen centre is a consequence of combining strain measurements from two specimens, one cut from each side of the laminate. Precise positioning of the sample, particularly for the cut depth, coupled with the sensitivity of the strain measurement (for certain cuts only several $\mu\text{m/m}$ were registered on the gauges), ensures that the strain profile can be obtained with a high degree of accuracy.

The stress values obtained agree well with the numerical predictions. The samples showed a large curvature before strain measurement, on average $9 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mm}^{-1}$ as measured with an adapted dial test indicator. When the stresses which relaxed out on demoulding to give this curvature are added to the measured stress profiles, it is clear that appreciably higher stress levels were present in the samples before demoulding.

CONCLUSIONS

The Successive Grooving Technique is proposed as a practical technique for the determination of the internal stresses within manufactured parts. The phenomenon of stress release as a result of cutting a groove across the thickness of a part has been exploited; the measured strain field induced in the part by the stress release can be described with a two-dimensional compliance model, and the individual layer stresses back-calculated from these measured strains.

The method requires no special sample preparation techniques. Local variations in the stress field can be determined with high accuracy. The influence of material anisotropy and/or geometric characteristics can be accounted for in the compliance coefficients; the scheme can be used for anisotropic or isotropic materials with a through-thickness internal stress profile.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was funded by the Swiss Federal Office for Education and Science (OFES) under contract no. OFES BR082, as a part of the European Commission BRITE-EURAM project no. BE5092. The contributions of Philippe Berguerand and Richard Phillips have been greatly appreciated.

REFERENCES

- 1) J.A. Nairn, and P. Zoller, *The development of residual thermal stresses in amorphous and semicrystalline thermoplastic matrix composites*, in Toughened Composites, ed. N.J. Johnston, ASTM Philadelphia, PA, USA, 328 - 341 (1987).
- 2) G. Jeronimidis and A.T. Parkyn, *Residual stresses in carbon fibre-thermoplastic matrix laminates*, Journal of Composite Materials, **22** (May), 401 - 415 (1988)
- 3) K.-S. Kim, H.T. Hahn, and R.B. Croman, *The effect of cooling rate on residual stress in a thermoplastic composite*, Journal of Composites Technology & Research, **11** (2), 47 - 52 (1989)
- 4) T.J. Chapman, J.W. Gillespie, R.B. Pipes, J.-A.E. Manson, and J.C. Seferis, *Prediction of process-induced residual stresses in thermoplastic composites*, Journal of Composite Materials, **24** (June), 617-643 (1990)
- 5) I.A. Birger, *Method for determining residual stresses in bars and plates*, Zavodskaya Laboratoriya, **28** (5), 599-604 (1962)
- 6) C.W. Bert and G.L. Thompson, *A method for measuring planar residual stresses in rectangular orthotropic materials*, Journal of Composite Materials, **2** (4), 244ff (1968)
- 7) J.-A.E. Manson and J.C. Seferis, *Process Simulated Laminate (PSL): a methodology for internal stress characterisation in advanced composite materials*, Journal of Composite Materials, **26** (3), 405-431 (1992)
- 8) R. Phillips, P. Kim, P. Sunderland and J.-A.E. Manson, *Influence of processing parameters on the dimensional stability of polymer composites*, Proceedings of the Workshop on Advanced Materials for High-Precision Detectors, Archamps, France, September 28-30, 167-174 (1994)